

THE COURAGE OF COTTON INDUSTRY WORKERS AT THE FRONT AND BEHIND THE FRONTS DURING WORLD WAR II

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Abstract. *This article is one of the leading industrial enterprises in our country during the Second World War, and the majority of the population worked in these enterprises. Since the food, clothing, and medical products needed for the war are mainly obtained from cotton, the services rendered by the cotton ginning workers at the front and behind the front are classified as bravery. The exploits of the workers of the cotton ginning factory have been historically observed on the basis of scientific sources on the example of the Surkhan oasis.*

Keywords: *Surkhandarya, World War II, Termiz cotton factory, Denov cotton factory, Sherabad cotton factory, industry, front.*

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the Second World War (September 1, 1939 - September 2, 1945) is considered one of the most destructive wars in the history of mankind. Nazi Germany, Nazi Italy, and militarist Japan, which had started the war, were on one side, and a group of countries belonging to the anti-fascist coalition were on the other. The Second World War can be considered a tragedy of the last century.

On September 1, 1939, Germany invaded Poland and started World War II. In the summer of 1940, at the official request of the SSSR, Romania gave Bessarabia and Northern Bukovina to the Soviets. In June 1940, Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania were accepted into the SSSR.[1] Thus, the SSSR tried to distance the war from its territory as much as possible. But even the secret Molotov-Ribbentrop pact with Germany could not save the USSR from war.

61 countries, approximately 80% of the world's population, participated in the Second World War. 110 million inhabitants of the countries participating in the war were mobilized for it. Military actions took place on the territory of 40 countries. During the war, 62 million people died, including 27 million citizens of the USSR.

On June 22, 1941, Nazi Germany launched an attack on the SSSR.[2] At the time of the attack on the SSSR, Germany has a much greater military and economic potential than the Soviet Union, and it prepares for war for a long time and intensively. As a result, the western borders of the SSSR were quickly occupied.

In 1941, 88 million people, or 40% of the total population of the SSSR, and 32% of workers and servants lived in the temporarily occupied territory. On the eve of the war, there were 31,850 plants, factories and other enterprises in the occupied territory of the SSSR, excluding small enterprises and workshops. In the first months of the war, the temporary loss of economically important regions and industrial centers had a severe impact on the work of all sectors of the national economy and caused the beginning of socio-economic and industrial "stagnation" in all regions of the Union. The end of 1941 the beginning of 1942 was the most difficult period for the economy of the Soviet Union, and there was an acute shortage of labor force, fuel, electricity, raw materials, and various materials in the national economy. The volume of gross industrial product

decreased by 1.9 times from June to December 1941. Only by December 1941, the decline in industrial production was stopped[3].

METHODS

In the article, based on the principles of impartiality, historical analysis, comparative and logical analysis, and chronological sequence, the courage of cotton ginning industry workers at the front and behind the front during the Second World War is explained on the basis of scientific sources.

RESULTS

Based on conceptual-methodical approaches, the research on the history of the courage of the workers of the cotton ginning industry at the front and behind the front during the Second World War is divided into two groups on the basis of periodical and problematic principles, including the first group of publications published during the years of Soviet power, the second group are studies created during the period of independence. During the Soviet period, Uzbekistan during the Second World War, a number of scientific works on the history of the cotton ginning industry were created, which were devoted to the development of the industry and the construction of industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan during the Soviet period. Among them, S. Ziyodullaev, J. Olmasboev, V. Kudryashov, K. Kasimov, Kh. Joraev, S. Karaboev, Sh. R. Marasulov, A. Joragulov, who are directly related to the research work under study, A. Orolov, K. Karimov's works can be cited[4]. Also, during this period, a number of dissertation works on the history of industry in Uzbekistan were completed. Examples of these are the studies of F. Ishakov, D. Babadzhanova and B. Hasanov.[5]

During the Soviet period, a number of works dedicated to the history of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions were created. These include the works of A. Roziev, D. Bichkov, L. Blinnikov, Kh. Rakhmankulov, A. Choriev, A. Karimov[6]. Also, in 1991, a group of authors published the book "Clips from the history of Surkhondarya" dedicated to the 50th anniversary of the establishment of Surkhondarya region[7]. This book also glorifies the role of the Communist Party in the socio-economic development of the region.

Thus, historians of the Soviet era approached the issue based on the interests of the communist ideology in covering the history of socio-economic and cultural processes that took place in Uzbekistan between 1945 and 1991. For this reason, the literature of this period exaggerates the advantages and achievements of the Soviet system, but does not comment on the existing problems. Such a situation requires the author to critically evaluate and analyze most of the information in the literature about this group.

The literature of the second group was created during the years of independence, in which socio-economic, cultural and political life of this period is analyzed in a critical spirit. During the years of independence, methodological works were created that reveal the essence of the Soviet era, as well as the real goals of the autocratic regime's policy towards Uzbekistan. For example, in the work of D. Alimova and A. Golovanov, the true nature of the administrative-command system and the processes of striving for independence are given. The struggle of the republic towards national independence is analyzed on a new methodological basis[8].

In the researches of I. Alimov and Q. Rajabov dedicated to the history of Uzbekistan during the Soviet period, the essence of socio-economic problems in the republic has been revealed[9].

In the research carried out during the years of independence, the conflicting situations that occurred in the socio-economic and cultural life of Uzbekistan in the 80s of the 20th century, the

“Cotton Case” and its consequences were revealed[10]. In the monographs of D. Bobojonova and A. Joraev, socio-economic processes in the Republic were analyzed in the last years of the Soviet era[11]. Especially during the Soviet era, the issues of cultural life in the republic were objectively analyzed in a completely new spirit in the studies of S.N. Tursunov, E.A. Qabulov, A.Q. Tukhtaev, T.R. Pardaev, Yu.Ergasheva, U.Koraboev, Q.Ergashev.

In the following years, scientific research studies were carried out, which investigated some aspects of the processes related to the industry and agriculture of the Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions during the Soviet era[12]. In addition, the history of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions is described in a new spirit in the books written by O.Jorakulov, S.Tursunov and M.Khudaykulov on the history of cities and districts of the southern regions[13].

DISCUSSION

With the beginning of the Second World War, the population of our country was forced to go to the front, the lack of labor force, the lack of specialist personnel, problems in the supply of food and other products led to a sharp reduction of production funds, and then a slow recovery. . For example, in 1941, industrial production was 72% compared to 1940, in 1942 - 68%, in 1943 - 76%, in 1944 - 84%, in 1945 - 88%. The national income in 1945 compared to 1940 was 83%, and industrial production was 92%. At the same time, the largest decline in industrial production occurred in 1942: 23% (77% by 1940)[14].

As part of the alliance, Uzbekistan participated in the war both directly and indirectly. In the 40s of the 20th century, the population of the Uzbek SSR was around 6.5 million, and about 1.5 million of them were involved in the war. More than 263,000 people lost their lives, 132,670 people went missing, and 60,452 compatriots returned from the war disabled[15]. 50 thousand 365 people who participated in the Second World War were sent from Surkhandarya region. This was more than 3.5% of the fighters sent to war from Uzbekistan. 4360 people from Kumkurgan district of Surkhandarya region were sent to the war, which is 8.65% of the total number sent from the region. 2094 of them died fighting bravely, 2260 returned to their country with victory, but with various injuries[16]. 5365 people (10.65%) went to war from Zharkurgan district, 3826 of them died, 1583 returned to Surkhandary with injuries[17]. Big losses were observed not only in industry, economy and agriculture, but also in population[18]. According to statistics, the population of the USSR decreased by 34.5 million people during the war years: on January 1, 1941 - 196.8 million, on January 1, 1946 - 162.3 million. Among the victims of the war were 13.7 million civilians, of whom 7.4 million were deliberately exterminated by the invaders, 2.2 million died in forced labor in Germany, and 4.1 million died of starvation during the occupation[19].

With the beginning of the war, the process of forming various groups of volunteers and going to the front began in Surkhandarya as well as in various regions of Uzbekistan. Cotton industry enterprises were not left out of these processes. For example, on June 23, 1941, a rally was held at the Termiz cotton factory, where the director of the factory, Ivanov, workers Pashkin, Bashkatova, Grachev and other speakers spoke and called everyone to fight for the defense of the Motherland. As a result, the majority of men at the factory went to the front. Among them, V. Vyalochkin and A. Mumikhin, locksmiths of the Termiz cotton ginning plant, voluntarily went to war[20]. The process started at the Termiz cotton ginning plant, which is the main industrial enterprise of the region, continued in other enterprises as well. Many of the workers working at the Denov cotton gin factory volunteered to go to the front. During the war, M.M. Zagodyakin (in 1942-1944) was the leader, and in those years three-shift work was organized. 29 people served

cocktails in the first brigade, 33 people in the second brigade, and 30 people in the third brigade. In addition, 20 people worked in the repair shop, 8 people in the construction team, and 11 people in the factory kindergarten. With this, workers who could not directly participate in the war for various reasons tried to fill the place of those who went to war. In April 1944, Erlekhman Ruvim Yakovlevich, who was appointed director of the Denov cotton ginning plant and served in this position until February 1950, also took part in the war until he was appointed to this position. R. Ya. Erlekhman was mobilized to the front on March 25, 1942, but after being wounded in the battle around Kharkov, he was released from military service and sent back to help behind the front. From April 1942, he started working at the “People’s Commissariat of the UzSSR” as the head of the Preparatory Department, and later he was transferred to the Denov cotton ginning plant. Erlekhman was the reason for appointing Ruvim Yakovlovich to this position. Because during the war, it was necessary to raise the industry, the cotton industry, which had weakened during the war, in Surkhandarya. He has a lot of experience in this field and started working in cotton ginning in 1920s. First, in 1925-1926, Erlekhman was responsible for receiving cotton at the Urganch cotton ginning factory belonging to the Uzpakhtasanoat system, then in 1926-1928, he was the head of the Koshkopir cotton receiving center, and in 1928, Khanka Head of the Preparatory Department of the Cotton Ginnery, in 1929 Head of the Preparatory Department of the Urganch Cotton Ginnery, in 1930 the Inspector of the “Main Cotton Committee”, in 1931 the current Sho’rchi (at that time In 1938, he gained considerable experience by working as an economist in the Preparatory Department of the “UzSSR Textile People’s Cooperative” as a temporary point manager for the establishment of a cotton receiving center in the Denov District. The appointment of experienced specialists indicates that the importance of Surkhandarya districts for cotton growing has increased. Among the workers of the Termiz and Denov factories, experts of various levels from the Khayrabad cotton ginning factory went to the front. The best workers of the plant for the defense of the motherland, namely the head of construction works Rybkin Vladimir Pavlovich, economist Kivyanin, foremen Maslov Ivan, Turkov Andrey, Kamal Sodikov, machinist Ovcharenko Petr, Skachkov Mikhail, Tikhonov Nikolai, firemen chief Nasakhin Mikhail, head of “Dzhinguaz” Yurtaev Sergey Polikarpovich, builder Titerin Nikolay Ivanovich, fire engineer L'vov Grigory, workers Odinaev Khairulla, Salimov Jalal, Parkhomenko Grigory, Sarimsokov Osha and others left.

CONCLUSION

The Second World War took place not only at the front, but also behind the front. One of the main tasks of the war was to provide food, clothes, and ammunition to the boys who were defending their country on the battlefields. In addition, after the departure of the main labor force working in agriculture and industry, men, it was necessary to fill their jobs, not to take pictures of production as much as possible, and to support the state in every way.

In a short time, the territory of Uzbekistan has become one of the important areas for many industrial enterprises, population and other service centers evacuated from the front areas.

With the outbreak of the war, the situation was aggravated by the fact that many enterprises, including defense industry enterprises located in the western regions of the country, were shut down as a result of the forced retreat of the Red Army. Until November 1941, 40% of the total population of the country lived in the territory of the occupied USSR. In addition, in the pre-war economy, 63% of coal mining, 68% of iron smelting, 58% of steel smelting, 60% of aluminum production, 38% of grain production, 84% of sugar production, as well as this 38% of the number

of cattle were raised in the regions[21]. Naturally, in such conditions, great efforts were required to ensure the uninterrupted operation of the entire country's industrial complex, to provide for the army and the population behind the front.

First of all, it was necessary that the enterprises located in the occupied territory should not fall into the hands of the Nazis and should not work for them, but should be preserved for the country. It was this task that was carried out as an unprecedented move in world history - a large amount of valuable goods, equipment and millions of people were quickly transported thousands of kilometers from the front and near-front regions. In addition to the transfer, the USSR also had the task of ensuring the production of its products in a new place as soon as possible. It is noteworthy that from July to December 1941, a total of 2,593 enterprises were evacuated from the threatened areas. Including 1,523 large enterprises, 1,360 of which were military enterprises, which were evacuated in the first months of the war[22].

As a result of military losses, as well as the evacuation of hundreds of enterprises, the production of gross industrial product decreased by 2.1 times from June to November 1941. The production of non-ferrous metal rolling, necessary for the production of military industrial products, has decreased by 430 times. The production of ball bearings, without which it is impossible to produce airplanes, tanks, and artillery, was reduced by 21 times[23].

In the years 1941-1945, more than 72,000 clothes for women fighters of the region, including 281 semi-fur coats, 270 fur coats, 709 fur coats, 1714 felt boots, 1975 warm coats, 1770 warm clothes, 384 cotton ones. those who prepared and sent the pants[24].

REFERENCES

1. Economy of the USSR during the Great Patriotic War // URL: http://www.great-country.ru/content/sss_r_stat/xoz_70/xoz_70-005.php.
2. <https://qomus.info/encyclopedia/cat-i/ikkinchi-jahon-urushi-uz/>.
3. Soviet economy during the Great Patriotic War of 1941–1945. – M.: Nauka, 1970. – P. 382.
4. Ziyadullaev S., Manokhin I. Sotsialisticheskaya promyshlennost Sovetskogo Uzbekistana. - Tashkent, 1949; Ulmasbaev J.N. Promyshlennoe razvitie Sovetskogo Uzbekistana. - Tashkent, 1958; Kudryashov V. Za pod'em narodnogo hozyaystva. - Tashkent, 1964; Kasymov K.K. Deyatel'nost' Kompartii Uzbekistana po razvitiyu tekstil'noy promyshlennosti. - Tashkent, 1974; Djuraev Kh. Promyshlennost' Uzbekistana: tempo, struktur i effektivnost'. - Tashkent, 1974.
5. Ishakov F.B. Tvorcheskaya aktivitiya rabochikh tekstilshchikov Uzbekistana v period razvitiya sotsializma (1959-1970 gg). Diss... kandida istoricheskix nauk. - Tashkent, 1975.
6. Roziev A. Surkhan-Sherabad agriculture. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1967; Bichkov D.A., Blinnikov L.I. Surkhandarya region. II (Brief spravochnik). - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1970.
7. Berdiev H., Ermatov H., Oltinov M., Toshpolatov J., et al. Scenes from the history of Surkhandarya. - Tashkent: Nur, 1991.
8. Alimova D., Golovanov A. Uzbekistan in 1917-1990: confrontation of ideas and ideologies. – Tashkent, 2002.
9. Alimov I., Rajabov Q. Increasing socio-political crisis and economic stagnation in Uzbekistan (1971-1985) // Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent, 2006. - P. 182-184.; Those authors: Uzbekistan on the way to independence (1985-1991). // National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. Volume 12. - Tashkent, 2006. - P. 184-185.

10. Oblomurodov N. Development of agricultural production in Uzbekistan in 1971-1990. Experience lessons, problems. Author's abstract. diss. doc. ist. Sci. – Tashkent, 1994.
11. Joraev A. Village and social life. - Tashkent, 1992; Bobojonova D. Socio-economic relations in Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Sharq, 1999.
12. Qabulov E. The history, experience and problems of the development of the light and food industry in the southern regions of Uzbekistan (1946-1960). Dissertation written for the degree of PhD in History. - Samarkand, 1994; Tursunov J.N. History of economic and social development of cities in Uzbekistan (primarily cities of Boysun, Shargun and Shurchi) (1971-1990) Autoref. diss. ist. science - Samarkand, 1995.
13. Tursunov S.N. Conditions and factors of decline of agricultural development of Uzbekistan (1946-1965) - Tashkent: Science, 1994; Tursunov S.N. Problems of improving housing and living conditions of the rural population (1946-1965). - Tashkent, 1994; Farmanov M. Mangu lit lamp. – Against, 1996; Khudoykulov M. Karshi desert. - Tashkent: Sharq, 1998; Tursunov S.N., Kichkilov H. Yearbook of Termiz. - Tashkent: Sharq, 2001; Tursunov S.N., Kabilov E.O. Pardayev T., Murtazoyev B.Kh. Surkhandarya is in the mirror of history. - Tashkent: Sharq, 2001.
14. Narodnoe hozyaystvo SSSR // URL: <http://mysteriouscountry.ru>.
15. <https://qomus.info/encyclopedia/cat-i/ikkinchi-jahon-urushi-uz>.
16. Qabulov E. First steps of Surkhandarya industry. - Termez, 1993. - P. 171.
17. Tursunov S., Eshboyev Q. Scenes from the history of Kumkoran. - Tashkent: New edition, 2018. - P. 189.
18. Tursunov S., Tokhtayev A., Annayeva Z. Scenes from the history of Zharkurgan. - Tashkent: New edition, 2018. - P. 88.
19. How much did the Victory cost? The Great Patriotic War in numbers // URL: http://gov.cap.ru/SiteMap.aspx?gov_id=102&id=460575
20. Qabulov E. First steps of Surkhandarya industry. - Termez, 1993. - P. 171.
21. Voznesensky N.A. The military economy of the USSR during the Patriotic War / In the book “N. Voznesensky” – M.: House of “Economic Newspaper”, 2009. –P. 111.
22. The national economy of the USSR over 70 years. – M.: State Statistics Committee of the USSR, 1987. – P. 43.
23. Voznesensky N.A. The military economy of the SSSR during the Patriotic War / In the book “N. Voznesensky” – M.: House of “Economic Newspaper”, 2009. –P. 112.
24. Kabulov E., Rajapova S. Great shares of the laborers of Surkhan valley during World War II // Look to the past. 2020, SI. – Pp.541-547.